

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOVEN FIBERGLASS COMPOSITE INTERLEAVED WITH GLASS NANOFIBERS

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Abstract

The present study describes the processing and mechanical characterization of S-2 glass fiber, EPON 862-EPIKURE curing agent W composite with and without interleaved Tetra Ethyl Ortho silicate (TEOS) chemically engineered glass nanofibers manufactured via electrospinning technique. Electrospun TEOS nanofibers were sintered to evaporate ethanol and reduce the fiber diameter to further increase the surface area and obtain chemically pure glass nanofibers. The heated Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (H-VARTM) method was used to fabricate the composite panel using epoxy resin system under similar flow and curing conditions. Test specimens were cut using a water jet machine following ASTM test standards for tension, compression, in plane shear, interlaminar shear and isopecu tests. Various mechanical properties that include strength, modulus, Poisson's ratio, shear modulus, fiber volume fraction and densities are measured; the corresponding modes of failure have been studied and compared. The S-2 glass fibers composites with electrospun TEOS nanofibers interface layers in the present study showed significant improvement in the in-plane shear strength and modulus, but only a slight enhancement in the tensile properties. However the compression strength and modulus as well as shear modulus showed a reduction. This could be due to pre-bend in the plies of the glass fiber and fold over elastic sizing due to the weave form of woven glass fiber. Estimated values of the elastic constants using simplified micromechanics equations for composite lamina are compared with experimental results. Present experimental results show significant improvement in the in-plane shear strength of the composite with electrospun nanofibers interface layers that could enhance the delamination characteristics of the S-2 fibers, epoxy composite system discussed in the present study.

1. Introduction

High performance S-2 glass fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites have been considered in aerospace, defense, automobile, wind turbine

structural applications due to their unique combination of properties such as strength, impact resistance, stiffness, temperature resistance, fatigue resistance, light weight and radar transparency compared to other conventional glass fibers [1]. In addition, they deliver better cost performance than aramid and carbon fibers.

However, the limitations of the woven roven technology are crimping of yarns that create stress concentration at cross over of the yarn reducing the strength [2]; increase in the misalignment angle of the fiber that reduces the compressive strength up to 20% [3]; woven surfaces pulled out from the resin that initiate the failure [4]. All inhibit their positive structural characteristics. Further, common cause of failures in composite laminates is due to delamination. Delamination in composite laminates can occur due to various loadings such as low velocity impact, fatigue, etc., and are critical due to their sub-surface nature. Conventional methods such as stitching and Z-pinning, while improving interlaminar properties in woven fiber composites, lead to a reduction of the in-plane properties [5-6]. Electrospun non-woven sheet of nanofibrous mat applied at interfacial regions offer a potential option to traditional treatments. The specific strength of glass composites is about two and half times that of steel, while the specific stiffness is only about one-half that of steel as shown in Table 1 [7]. The use of electrospun glass nanofibers formulated form TEOS contribute a similar material system compatible with epoxy resin. The use of such nanofibers interface layers in traditional woven fiber glass-epoxy composites is the focus of present study.

Table 1 Typical specific properties of steel and composites [7]

Material	Density (g/cc)	Tensile Specific strength (MPa/g /cc)	Tensile specific modulus (GPa/g/cc)
Steel	8.0	64.4	24.1
Woven glass/epoxy	2.2	166.8	13.5
Carbon/epoxy	1.6	1443.0	89.9

The present study focuses on the fabrication and characterization of fiberglass composite laminates interleaved with glass nanofiber. The use of Tetra Ethyl Orthosilicate (TEOS) chemically engineered glass nanofibers manufactured using electrospinning technique interleaved within woven glass fiber composite laminates is investigated, and their effect on various mechanical characteristics including tensile, compressive, shear are presented

2. Electrospinning Process

In the present work, electrospinning process is employed to produce random nanofiber mat and is used as additional interleaving layer between woven glass fiber layers. Electrospinning uses an electric field created by a high voltage power supply to generate fibers of varying diameters formed due to Taylor cone effect from a solution gelatin (sol-gel) to a ground collector. The process originally developed around 1934 by Formahals [8] has gained the attention of several areas including mechanical engineering and the bio-medical fields such as biomedical tissue engineering and drug enhancements in the recent years [9-10].

Electrospinning is a non-contact drawing process in which a polymer droplet emanating from the tip of spinneret is attracted towards a grounded collector due to the applied electrical potential difference and surface tension of the droplet. The electro-static forces cause the droplet to stretch, resulting into a bending instability and whipping of the elongated jet producing fibers of nanometer and submicron diameter (nanofibers) with exceptionally long lengths. Evaporation of solvents takes place as the nanofibers are deposited on to a grounded collector. By controlling process parameters and properties of the polymer, ceramic or composite starting solution, fiber diameters ranging from 3 - 900 nanometers can be produced [11]. Electrospinning is a fast and low cost manufacturing technique that can be easily scaled up.

2.1 Electrospinning of Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) nanofibers

The TEOS solution prepared for electrospinning is adopted from Brincker [9]. 98% TEOS solution is mixed with Ethanol (1 part) by volume. Five drops of HCl used as catalyst is added slowly to dilute the mixture using de-ionized water to a 1:50 ratio. The solution was kept for aging in the ambient condition of 72 °F at 44% humidity. When the weight of solution reduces 48-55% after a period 44-48 hours of evaporation, the solution viscosity is in the range

of 100-400 centipoise, resulting in a solution consistency that is good for the electrospinning process. Fig. 1 a shows the set up for the electrospinning, a solution droplet is fed to the spinneret tip at a controlled rate using a programmable dispensing pump. The dispensing pump employed is Model NE-1000 Multi-Phaser supplied by New Era Pump Systems Inc. and can hold a syringe up to 50mm in diameter. This pump can dispense solution at rates ranging from 0.1 ml /min. to 10 ml / min.

Fig.1a Electrospinning setup

Fig.1b Electrospinning jet

The solution droplet at the tip of spinneret is acted upon by electro-hydrodynamic forces. Electrical forces are due to the potential difference between the spinneret and collector plate. Spinneret is kept at a positive potential and collector plate is usually kept grounded. FC Series, 120 Watt Regulated High Voltage DC Power Supply supplied by Glassman High Voltage Inc. was used to maintain potential difference of up to 20kV between spinneret and collector. The distance between tip of the spinneret and collector plate was kept at 20.5cm. Because of this applied potential difference, the solution droplet at the tip of the spinneret acquires a positive charge on the surface. The hydro-dynamic force is due to surface tension of the liquid solution. This solution droplet gets attracted towards collector and forms a 45° semi-angle at the tip called as

Taylor Cone [12]. If the viscosity of solution is sufficient to provide stringiness, there is elongation of droplet into a jet, which under the action of whipping and "Bending Instability"[13] forms fiber in the range of 3nm to 1 μ m depending on the solution properties. In the present work these TEOS nanofiber were collected on a Teflon sheet attached to the collector to reduce the damage of the fiber after evaporation.

2.1.1 Sintering of the TEOS fiber

After one week of evaporation of ethanol from the fibrous sheet at ambient conditions. TEOS nanofibers were soft. Fig. 2 shows the SEM images for the TEOS nanofiber before sintering. The nanofibers were in the range of 300 - 500nm.

Fig.2 SEM micrograph of electrospun TEOS nanofibers before sintering

The TEOS nanofiber mats were folded and stacked together and sintered at temperature 600⁰ C for 6 hours [14] using Furnace 6000 supplied by Barnstead thermodyne Inc. After sintering TEOS nanofibers became brittle with a reduced diameter range of 250 – 450 nm as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3 SEM micrograph of electrospun TEOS nanofibers after sintering at temperature 600 °C

TEOS nanofibers were interleaved between the woven fabric layers of the composite lamina to form S-2 glass fiber epoxy composite with interleaved TEOS based glass nanofibers.

3. Materials

S-2 plain weave woven glass fiber, TEOS electrospun nanofibers are the fiber materials employed. The resin system used was epoxy resin from Miller Stephenson chemical Inc. The details of these materials are given next.

3.1 Glass Fibers

The woven roving of BGF was chosen due to its wide use for structural applications and is also inexpensive. BGF 240(S-2 463-AA-250) consist of single fibers and glass roving with BGF industries style 240 sizing for ease of handling, quick wet out, and is compatible with EPON resin 862/EPIKURE curing agent W system. The areal weight was 24.00 Oz/sqyd and the construction is balanced with 50% of the fiber in warp direction and the remaining 50% of the fibers in the weft direction. The ratio was verified by pic count which was the number of rovings per inch. The pic count was 5 in warp direction and 5 in the weft direction in the fibers supplied by the BGF industries with the designation of BGF-240 S-2 glass fiber whose architecture is shown in Fig.4 [15].

Fig. 4 BGF 240 S-2 glass fabric (warp-vertical direction)

3.2 Resin

The matrix used was a commercial Miller Stephenson Chemical Inc [16] EPON resin 862, a phenolformaldehyde polymer glycidyl ether and EPIKURE W Curing agent of diethylmethyl benzenediamine 684779-98-1. Resin 862/EPIKURE curing agent W resin system was formulated with mix ratio of 100:26.4 for H-VARTM (Heated Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer molding) process. This resin has been used due to high wettability, good balance of mechanical, adhesive, and electrical properties and also exhibits good chemical resistance, superior physical properties. In addition, this resin provides superior mechanical properties in the composite such as impact resistance, fatigue life.

Fig. 8 Cure and post cure time–temperature cycle

4.2. Fiber volume fraction

The volume fraction of both the composite panels with and without nanofibers was obtained and is shown in the Table 2. The volume fraction is calculated following both the matrix burn off test according to ASTM D 3171-99 [19] and the areal density method. The fiber volume fraction of the S-2 glass fiber and TEOS nanofiber interleaved composite panels was 58.61% and 58.73% by matrix burn off test method and 57.21% and 68.68% by areal density method respectively as shown in Table2.

Table 2 Fiber volume fraction

	Fiber volume fraction, v_f (%)		Density(g/cc)
	Matrix Burn-off method	Areal density method	
S-2 Glass fiber	58.61	57.21	2.0754
S-2 glass fiber with TEOS naofiber	58.73	68.68	2.2575

5. Experimental Mechanical Characterization

Test coupons were cut as per the layout shown in Fig. 9 using the water jet machine; washed and removed grease, dirt, and contaminants from the surface and subsequently grinded on the surface to obtain smooth and parallel surfaces to avoid the bending and twisting during tests. The tension, compression, inter-laminar shear specimens were tabbed using a NEMA grade G-10 epoxy glass laminate and toughened 3 M epoxy adhesive. The adhesive was cured at room temperature for 24 h in vacuum bag and then cured at 150 °F for three hour in a computer controlled oven. Strain gages were fixed along the warp direction on the specimen to capture data between 1000 to 10000 μ s using the tabbed and strain-gage instrumented specimens for tension compression, inter-laminar shear, and

iosipescu in-plane shear characterization as per the ASTM test standards [19]. All the axial strains were measured by extensometer and longitudinal and transverse strain were measured by strain gages. Strain gages were attached the specimens and differed as per the tests.

Fig.9 Layout for specimen

Tension: Five specimens were strain gaged in both longitudinal and transverse direction to obtain a measure of the Poisson’s ratio and Modulus of elasticity.

Compression: Five specimens were strain gaged in the axial direction but maintained the gage length of 1 in so as to fix the gage on the surface of the specimen.

Iosipescu shear: The strain gages were fixed at $\pm 45^\circ$ to loading axis, in the middle of the specimen away from the notch and along the loading axis to measure the shear response. Five test specimens were employed

In plane shear: Five specimens with gages fixed at $\pm 45^\circ$ to loading axis, in the middle of the specimen along the loading axis to measure the shear response.

For tension and compression tests, five coupons of S-2 glass fiber composite with and without TEOS electrospun nanofiber interleaving were pulled. The mean/standard deviation for tensile strength were about 79 ksi/ 4.93 and 77.36 ksi/ 4.29, 31.55 ksi/2.33 and 34.46 ksi/4.65and respectively.

For in-plane shear tests, five coupons of S-2 glass fiber composite with and without TEOS electrospun nanofiber interleaving were tested. The mean/standard deviation for tensile strength and modulus were 15 ksi/ 0.52 and 14 ksi/ 2.16 respectively.

For interlaminar shear strength, five coupons of S-2 glass fiber composite with and without TEOS electrospun nanofiber interleaving were tested. As

per ASTM standards with a mean/standard deviation for interlaminar strength were 5.2ksi/0.44and 4.3ksi/0.3

5.1. Tension test

Tensile tests were conducted as per the ASTM Standard Test Method (D 3039/D 3039-08) for tensile properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials. Blue hill system on the Instron machine was used to record the load, displacement, and strain gage reading through a channel system until the specimen fractured. During the initiation, progression, and final fracture, the failure loads and modes were recorded. From test data, tensile modulus, strength, and Poisson's ratio were determined as per the ASTM standard. The average values and standard deviations were calculated and the average values are listed in Table 3. The variation in data from all tests performed was less than 6% for S-2 glass fiber and 6% for the S-2 glass fiber with TEOS nanofiber interleaving. The corresponding composite modulus of elasticity variation was 4% in the case of composite with interleaved fibers. The minimum data scatter confirmed consistency and quality of the panel fabrication, specimen preparation, testing. The failure mode showed fiber bulging in the direction of warp due to stress reversal and fracture at the middle of the gage. The S-2 glass fiber specimens failed by longitudinal fiber fracture at different locations in the middle of different plies with delamination occurring due to the compression shock waves caused by the fiber breakage. The S-2 glass fiber with TEOS nanofiber showed same mode of failure but breakings of fibers were slightly away from middle of the specimen with bulging occurring due to delamination and compression shock wave caused by the breaking of fiber [20].

5.2. Compression test

Compression tests were conducted as per the ASTM Standard Test Method (D 3410/D 3410M-03) for compressive properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials with unsupported gage section by shear loading. Short gauge lengths of 1in were used to avoid buckling instability. Load, displacement, and strain gage reading were recorded continuously until the specimen fractured. The data recorded was used to determine compression strength and modulus. After testing edges of the specimens were micro-graphed with an optical microscope as shown in Fig. 10-11. Failure was observed to initiate due to the micro buckling of the fiber in the specimens due to kinking followed by collapse similar to that of unidirectional composite

[20] in the case of S-2 glass fiber. Glass fiber showed ductile type of failure whereas S-2 with TEOS nanofiber showed more kinking followed by the collapse of the composite due to the micro buckling. More fiber kinking occurred when compared to the non-TEOS composite as shown in Fig. 10. The compression modulus and strength of all the specimens for the two types of glass fiber composite with and without TEOS nanofiber systems were calculated and average values are listed in Table 3. The coefficient of variation of the strength is less than 5% for S-2 glass fiber composite and about 3% in the S-2 glass fiber composite with interleaved TEOS nanofibers mats.

Fig.10 Typical compression failure for S-2 glass fibers with TEOS nanofiber

Fig.11 Typical compression failure for S-2 glass fibers

a) Warp direction b) At fiber level

Fig.12 Typical Iosipescu failure for S-2 glass fibers composite

a) Warp direction b) At fiber level

Fig.13 Typical Iosipescu failure for S-2 glass fibers composite with TESO nanofiber

5.3 In-plane shear testing and characterization

5.3.1 Inter laminar shear strength (ILSS) test

Tests were conducted using the modified short beam shear (MSBS) testing method [21], and the ILSS was calculated from the failure load. The failure modes from the failed specimen showed a typical near mid-plane delamination [20]. The average values and standard deviation of ILSS for all five specimens are calculated and listed in Table 3. The coefficient of variation of this test data is less than 7%.

5.3.2 Iosipescu test

In this test a shear force transmitted through a section between two edges of V- notches will produce a nearly uniform stress across the section. Tests were conducted on Wyoming Iosipescu test fixture supplied by MTT testing fixtures. Load, displacement, and strain gage readings were recorded continuously until the specimen failed. The data recorded is used to determine the shear modulus from the initial slope of the shear stress-shear strain plot at 0.2% offset shear strength. The modes of failure and the breaking of fiber laminates are shown in Fig.12-13. The failure at V- notch section is shown by white region show sliding of glass fiber in the composite with and without TEOS nanofiber. The average and standard deviation of the shear modulus and 0.2% offset shear strength were calculated and is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Summary of Mechanical properties of composites in direction of wrap

Properties		S-2 glass fiber	S-2 glass fiber with TEOS nanofiber
Volume fraction of fiber V_f (%)		57.19	55.92
Tension	Strength MPa (ksi)	533.4 (77.36)	544.8 (79.01)
	Modulus GPa (msi)	31.03 (4.5)	24.6 (3.57)
	Poisson's ratio	0.15	0.13
Compression	Strength MPa (ksi)	237.6 (34.46)	217.5 (31.55)
	Modulus GPa (msi)	26.04 (3.77)	16.40 (2.38)
	In-plane shear	Strength MPa (ksi)	44.70 (6.48)
In-plane shear	Modulus (msi) GPa	0.45 (3.10)	0.39 (2.72)
	Inter-laminar shear	Strength MPa (ksi)	29.6 (4.3)

6. Discussions

The properties of S-2 glass fiber composites with and without interleaved TEOS nanofibers layers from various mechanical tests are summarized in Table 3.

6.1 Tension properties

The S-2 woven roving glass composite have equal stiffness in direction of fill and warp due to the equal number of strands in both directions with equal number of picks(5) per inch. The Tensile modulus and strength of the S-2 glass fiber composite without interleaving of TEOS nanofibers in the present work are 31.03 GPa and 533.4 MPa respectively. Due to similar tow distribution in both directions, tensile modulus and strength in the fill/weft direction will be same test were not performed in the fill direction. The tensile modulus of S-2 glass fiber composite interleaved with TEOS nanofiber layer interleaving are 24.6 GPa and 544.8 MPa respectively. The reduction of the modulus could be due to a reduction in volume fraction from 57.19% to 55.92%. The strong adhesion between two plies of glass fiber interleaved by TEOS random nanofiber mat could contribute to the small increase in tensile strength reported in Table 3. The tensile strength obtained in the present test is increased slightly by.13% while the modulus is decreased by 21%.

Stress-strain behavior obtained is smooth until maximum stress: the stress versus strain curve

showed knee formation and subsequent deviation after initial linear variation [20]. This is due to the initial failure by matrix cracking; the fiber in tows is not straight and elongated during the initial load and subsequently breaks at the ultimate tensile strength as shown in Fig.14. Poisson's ratios of the glass composites with and without TEOS nanofiber material showed the effect of interleaving of the TEOS nanofiber between woven glass fiber and the plies. The variation could be due to strong adhesion between the woven glass fiber plies and TEOS nanofiber interleaving layer.

Fig.14 Stress-Strain behavior of glass fiber composite in tension test

6.2. Compression properties

Compression strength of polymer glass fiber composite depends on the type of fiber, sizing and the matrix as well on adhesion of the plies in the composite. Present test show that S- 2 epoxy fiber composite with TEOS interleaved nanofiber in between glass fiber plies shows a reduction in compressive strength and modulus. The percent reduction of compressive strength and compressive modulus are 8.4% and 37.01% respectively. The TEOS nanofibers could break easily due to the brittle nature of TEOS nanofiber. Further, pre bending of the fiber and fold over elastic (FOE) sizing are the possible reasons for reduction of compression properties.

6.4 In-plane shear properties

6.4.1 Iosipescu Test

The sliding of the fiber layers over each other are resisted by matrix and also matrix transfer the stress across the composites layers. The Iosipescu test result showed nonlinear behavior due to the softening of matrix. This nonlinear stress- strain

behavior shows an accumulation of crack in the matrix leading to failure initiation. The modulus is reduced in the case of composite with TEOS nanofiber layer interleaving from 2.62 GPa to 1.93 GPa and the strength was found to increase from 44.7 MPa to 54.7 MPa. The moduli in S-2 glass fiber composite is higher due to its better fiber nesting architecture; however lower modulus in the S-2 glass fiber composite with TEOS interleaving layer could be due to the brittle nature of the TEOS nanofiber. The in-plane shear strength increase is possibly due to the additional strength from TEOS nanofiber interleaved between the plies.

6.5 Inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS)

S-2 glass fibers with TEOS nanofiber interleaved showed better shear strength due to better nesting between fiber layers provided by interleaving TEOS nanofiber layer increasing the adhesion between the plies. The inter-laminar shear strength in the present work increased from 29.6 MPa to 35.9 MPa. Thus ILSS in the composite has increased resistance to the shearing of fibers by nearly 21 % due to interleaving of TEOS nanofibers and its associated strengthening.

6.6 Estimation of elastic constant

The elastic constant used for the matrix, fiber and TEOS nanofibers in a simplified composite micromechanics approach based on Chamis Equations [22] is shown in Table 4. These elastic constants are used to calculate estimated value of elastic constant of S-2 glass epoxy composites with and without TESO nanofiber interleaving layers. The values obtained from “LAMINATOR” analysis of composite laminates based on classical laminate plate theory are shown in Table 5. To calculate the elastic constant for S-2 glass composite with TEOS nanofiber interleaving layer, the properties of TEOS nanofiber are assumed as isotropic material [23]. The comparison of experimental and estimated values of modulus of elasticity, Poisson’s ratio and shear modulus for S-2 glass fiber epoxy composite with and without TEOS nanofiber interleaving layer is listed in Table 5.

Table 4 Fiber and resin properties used in the prediction [22, 23]

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}
S-2 glass fiber	85.49	85.49	35.64	0.2
EPON resin	3.44	3.44	1.28	0.35
TEOS nanofiber	2.75	2.75	1.35	0.25

Table 5 Comparison of result for with and without TEOS nanofibers

Material	Property	Approach		
		Experiment	Estimation	
S-2 Glass fiber	Tensile	E_{11}	31.03	31.85
	Modulus (GPa)	E_{22}	31.03	31.85
	Poisson’s ratio	ν_{12}	0.15	0.154
	In-pane shear modulus(GPa)	G_{12}	3.61	4.06
S-2 Glass fiber with TEOS nanofiber	Tensile	E_{11}	24.6	28.92
	Modulus (GPa)	E_{22}	24.6	28.92
	Poisson’s ratio	ν_{12}	0.13	0.155
	In-pane shear modulus(GPa)	G_{12}	3.10	2.72

6.7 Comparison of mechanical properties

Mechanical properties of woven roving S- 2 glass fiber epoxy composite with and without electrospun TEOS nanofiber interleaving layer experimentally and estimation are compared in Table 5. This shows that the estimated values employing composite laminate analysis using “LAMINATOR” analysis and the experimental result for modulus of elasticity and Poisson’s ratios are in good comparison; however the estimated shear modulus is higher. Also the thickness may vary in the fibrous mat and modulus of TEOS nanofiber calculated by previous research may have effect on the estimated value.

7. Conclusion

Electrospinning was used to electrospun TEOS nanofiber in the form of random mat with isotropic properties and sintered at 600°C for 6 hours in the stacked form. TEOS electrospun nanofiber mats were interleaved between the woven S-2 glass ply layers in the half of portion of the panel with a single interleaved TEOS nanofiber layer between each of the four layers of the woven S-2 glass fiber plies. Both sections of the composite layup was vacuum

bagged and infused with the same resins using H-VARTM process to fabricate S-2 glass fiber composites with EPON rein 862 and EPIKURE W curing agent. The fabricated composite panel was of superior quality with no dry fiber region, low voids and higher fiber volume content. The fiber volume fraction for S-2 glass fiber composite and S-2 glass fiber composite with TEOS electrospun nanofiber interleaving layers were 57.19% and 55.92% respectively.

A comparison of the S-2 glass fiber composites and S-2 glass with TEOS electrospun nanofiber layer interleaved composites through various mechanical characterization tests performed indicates:- Tensile test strength increased slightly by about 2% with a decrease in tensile modulus by about 20%. In compression test, the strength and modulus are decreased by 8.4% and 36.8% respectively. This could be due to the brittleness of the electrospun TEOS nanofiber; S-2 glass fibers not being straight with bend and fold over elastic (FOE) sizing as well as the low volume fiber fraction. The interlaminar shear strength was found to increase by nearly 21% and in plane shear strength increased about 22%, thus improving the delamination of the plies during the shearing.

Using simplified micromechanics equation employing the constituent properties, the composite laminate elastic constant are calculated and compared. The experimental results obtained showed good comparison in most cases expect in the case of shear modulus.

In summary, the use of electrospun TEOS nanofiber interleaved layers in the S-2 glass fiber composite clearly showed a significant improvement in the interlaminar shear strength impacting the delamination characteristic of the composite and their usefulness for structural application.

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